

ASSOCIATION OF PARENTING STYLES WITH THE PREFERENCE FOR THE TREATMENT OF ORAL HABITS IN 5-12 YEAR OLD CHILDREN IN NAGPUR CITY: A QUESTIONNAIRE BASED SURVEY

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ABSTRACT: Parents are mostly unaware regarding the treatment of oral habits in spite of knowledge resources available now days. Parenting styles have remarkable impact on overall physical and emotional development of a child. Parental demands are often observed as the behavior control which might in turn help to control oral habits in children as well as preference for the treatment of oral habits. Therefore, the present study is undertaken to assess the association of parenting styles with preference for treatment of oral habits in children.

KEYWORDS: Parenting Styles, Oral Habits, Preference for Treatment, preventive dental procedures

INTRODUCTION

In Indian scenario, Pediatric Dentistry is yet an upcoming separate speciality and awareness of this being a specialty is less as compared to the western countries where it is an established practice as adjuvant with Preventive Dentistry. Many parents are still unaware about the role of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry into their child's life.¹ Primary teeth are still of a low concern in India as they will exfoliate, but the severe consequences of untreated oral habits in children have still not enlightened the mind of parents. Parenthood have been described as exhibiting shifts in parenting skills and certain strategies that may influence their choices in promoting routine oral health behavior among children reinforced at home. Most of the times these treatments are delayed by the parents or caretakers just for the reason that they don't want their child to suffer the anxiety and discomfort of undergoing dental treatment.² Most of the treatment for cessation of oral habits requires patient's cooperation which in turn can be influenced by the parents. This requires mass awareness regarding treatment of oral habits in children.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To rule out the association between the parenting styles with knowledge of preference for the treatment of oral habits in 5-12 year old children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three hundred children aged between 5-12 years were clinically examined for the presence of oral habits. Complete intraoral and extraoral clinical records and case history was noted down. The parenting styles were measured by parenting style dimension questionnaire (PSDQ).

Table 1: Definition of four parenting styles.³

Authoritative	High parental responsiveness and high parental demand; Warmth and involvement, reasoning/induction, demographic participation
Authoritarian	Low parental responsiveness but high parental demand; Clear parental authority, unquestioning obedience and punitive strategies
Permissive	High parental responsiveness but low parental demand; Tolerance, general acceptance of child's decisions and tendencies to ignore child's misbehavior
Neglectful	Low parental responsiveness and low parental demand

After the assessment of parenting styles of all the parents who are participating in the study, the questionnaires were distributed to them. The questionnaire consisted of close ended questions. After they have completely filled the questionnaire it was attached along with the sheet of clinical records. They all were assessed regarding the knowledge and preference for the treatment of oral habits and its association with parenting styles. The data chart was also prepared along where the data entry as done for the assessment.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

The children aged between 5-12 years were included in the study those who were diagnosed with any of the oral habit such as Thumb sucking, mouth breathing, nail biting, lip biting, bruxism or any other existing self injurious habits. Parents who agreed for participation in the study.

CONSENT

Informed consent was taken from the parents of the children included in the study prior to filling of questionnaire along with the child's assent.

RESULTS

Out of the total questionnaires distributed (300), 33 were excluded due to incomplete/inappropriate data. Therefore, total 267 questionnaires were used for the preparation of data chart. Out of 267, 140 were fathers and 127 were mothers who participated in the study. Majority of parents are unaware of oral habits in children which is not associated with the parenting style. Permissive parents agreed that oral habits are not normal in children whereas other parenting styles disapprove this fact.

Majority of parents think that oral habits can be corrected itself once the child grows up, so no need of any treatment for the same. Major group of parents were unaware of the fact that their child practices oral habits. Only around 6% of them were aware about the oral habits in children. Parents were unaware about the fact that oral habits can cause oral deformities.

As per the authoritarian parents, it is important to visit dentist if the child practices oral habits, whereas other parental group disagree with this fact.

Majority of the authoritative parents agree to treat oral habits of their children, whereas other groups showed slight disagreement.

DISCUSSION

In previous studies the type of parenting style is seen as one of the factors influencing the child's overall oral health care. They are broadly classified as authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful. Variety in parenting styles may influence on how they encouraging routine oral health behaviours in their children and oral hygiene measures that are reinforced at home.³ Dental treatment may be delayed due to parent's behaviour that could not bear that the child would not be able to suffer the possible consequences of procedural measures.²

Oral habits such as thumb sucking, finger biting, or finger sucking, tongue thrusting, lip biting , or lip sucking, bruxism, mouth breathing have proved to be influential during the growth of jaws . These oral habits, if persist beyond certain developmental age, can cause disturbances in normally developing teeth, occlusion and surrounding oral tissues.

Most of the parents were aware that their children are practising oral habits that may become harmful. The knowledge, attitude and behavior of parents towards the dental treatments which are required can influence their child to a great extent in building a positive dental attitude. Against this outline, the study was conducted with the objective to assess the parental knowledge of the importance they give to primary teeth and to evaluate their attitudes towards the treatment of oral habits and acceptance of preventive procedures. The way of parenting styles has influence child's behaviour on how they manage their own oral health or how on they react with dentist during dental check-up.¹

CONCLUSION

Parenting styles may influence the physical and emotional development of children. It has been observed that attitude and awareness among parents regarding regular dental visits and importance of accepting preventive dental procedures at an early age is limited. Therefore the need for awareness regarding oral habits in children has to increase the speed to reach the masses. Authoritative parenting style posses the importance of treating oral habit which is not present in other group of parenting.

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